

Next generation Alkaline Membrane Water Electrolysers with Improved Components and Materials

MEA PRODUCTION

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Table of Content

0	Summary	5
1	Introduction.....	6
2	First Approach: Catalyst coated Membranes	8
2.1	Ink formulations and MEA preparation	8
2.1.1	MEAs from DLR (Oldenburg).....	8
2.1.2	MEAs from CEA	9
2.2	MPL/PTL for CCM approach	10
2.3	MEA testing.....	11
3	Second approach: Catalyst coated Substrates	15
3.1	MPL/PTL for CCS approach	15
3.2	CCS electrodes preparation and single cell testing (4-25 cm ²)	16
3.2.1	At CEA	16
3.2.2	At DLR	17
3.3	CCS stack electrodes preparation (200 cm ²).....	18
4	Conclusion.....	20
5	References	21

List of Tables

Table 1. CCM electrodes recipes (Catalyst spray coating on the membrane)	8
Table 2. Ink recipes for CCM MEA by spray coating at CEA	9
Table 3. Detailed CCMs preparation at CEA	10
Table 4. Summary of the second batch of MEA sent to DLR(Stuttgart)	12
Table 5. Properties of CCM MEA from DLR(Oldenburg)	13
Table 6. CCS electrode CEA recipes	16
Table 7. DLR ink recipe.....	18

List of Figures

Figure 1. Picture of the three CCMs	8
Figure 4. CCM delamination after activation MEAs from CEA	9
Figure 2. CCMs MEA	10
Figure 3. Picture of various vacuum plasma spray (VPS) MPL on different meshes	11
Figure 4. Polarization curves CEA MEAs with various MPL structures in pure water at 45°C	11
Figure 5. Polarization curves comparison in pure water at 45°C	12
Figure 6. Picture of CEA MEAs after chemical activation	13
Figure 7. Polarization curve of DLR MEA	13
Figure 8. Side view of stainless steel felt PTL with Nicke MPL coating on tope side	15
Figure 9. Polarization curve in 25cm ² Propuls cell	16
Figure 10. Highest performances with highly loaded electrodes in 2cm ² single cell	17

0 Summary

This deliverable summarizes recipes and protocols that were used to prepare MEAs within the NEWELY project. During the project, most of the tested MEAs were produced by either DLR Oldenburg or by CEA. We have reached the NEWELY milestone with catalyst coated substrate (CCS) MEAs. The produced MEAs were composed by OXYGN-N and H2GEN-M catalysts at the anode and cathode side respectively and supplied by CENmat. The ionomer was prepared with Poly(styrene-ethylenebutylene-styrene) (PSEBS) functionalized with 1,4-Diazabicyclo[2.2.2]octane (DABCO). The membrane was supplied as a thin film of 60 μm and the ionomer was the polymer dissolved either in Toluene (at CEA) or in Chloroform (at DLR Oldenburg) supplied by the Institute of Macromolecular Chemistry (IMC). Polybenzimidazole nanofibers mat covalently cross-linked with trimethylamine group was used as a second class of membrane and was tested in CCS-like MEA. These membranes were supplied by KIST.

The catalyst loading of the electrode were 4 mg/cm^2 and the catalyst/ionomer weight ratio was 90/10. The coating procedure was spray coating at the both laboratories. However, at DLR Oldenburg an automatic SONOTEK spray coating was used for preparing 25 and 200 cm^2 electrodes, while at CEA a manual spray device was used for 2 and 25 cm^2 electrodes size.

It was found that for a large electrodes production, the chloroform may lead to a better ink stability in comparison with Toluene. DLR experienced a decantation of the ink with time with the latter solvent. At CEA, such an instability was not observed, probably because, the spraying time was shorter. To circumvent this issue, IMC recommended the chloroform as the most suitable solvent.

Lastly, despite poor performances at the start of the project due to testing conditions in pure water electrolyte, some attempts to prepare catalyst coated membrane (CCM) was made. We succeed to prepare CCM-MEA by bar coating directly onto the membrane and by decal transfer method on Fumatech membrane. These approaches could be reconsidered for subsequent work for preparing CCM MEAs.

1 Introduction

Green hydrogen is one of the most promising solutions for the decarbonisation of society. Alkaline water electrolysis (AWE) is already a mature technology but its large footprint makes it inadequate for producing the energy vector at GW scale. Proton exchange membrane water electrolysis (PEMWE) on the other hand is compact but its dependence on iridium and other expensive materials poses a serious threat for up-scaling. Anion exchange membrane water electrolysis (AEMWE) combines the benefits of both technologies. However, its key performance indicators (KPI) do not reach commercial requirements and are lacking competitiveness. NEWELY project aimed to redefine AEMWE, surpassing the current state of AWE and bringing it one step closer to PEMWE in terms of efficiency but at lower cost. The three main technical challenges of AEMWE: membrane, electrodes and stack were addressed. NEWELY's target was to demonstrate in a 5-cell stack with 200 cm² electrodes a high performance and long lifetime using the project's new materials and stack technology. Dilute KOH supply and in the first part of the project also pure water supply to the stack were applied to reduce the system components' corrosion.

This report presents the work in the project to develop electrodes and MEAs (membrane electrode assemblies) achieving the target performance and supplying the project stack.

The ink recipe and the MEA configuration have a large influence on the final performance of the electrochemical system. Indeed, a non-optimized ionomer content may drastically reduce the performances [1] and no binder negatively impacts the durability [2].

Generally, two kinds of MEAs are considered. On one hand, the CCS (Catalyst Coated Substrate) MEA, whereby the active layer is coated on the porous substrate such as felt or foam on the anode, and carbon Gas Diffusion Layer (GDL) on the cathode. On the second hand the CCM (Catalyst Coated Membrane) MEA whereby the active layers are deposited on the membrane, either by direct coating on the membrane or by decal transfer method.

Most of MEA in literature [3-4] seems to be prepared using the CCS approach. However, some papers report on hybrid CCS anode and CCM cathode [5] arguing that the anode interface need a stronger mechanical strength and such behaviour was not reached with CCM. On the cathode side, the mechanical stress was less important since the authors have tested the cell in dry cathode mode.

Besides the type of MEA, the ink recipe also impacts the electrochemical response. The first parameter to be considered is the ratio catalyst/ionomer. It was reported that an excessive amount of ionomer may negatively affect the cell performances [1][6]. The performances improve with the ionomer content at the beginning. However, there is a threshold where an excessive amount of ionomer leads to an increase of the electrical resistance of the electrode and block the active sites from reactants. This is the case with PTFE binder for instance. With anion exchange ionomers, the excessive swelling may collapse the electrode and therefore decrease its performances accordingly [7].

Lastly, another element, which is rarely reported, is that a large amount of ionomer forms an additional permeation barrier that reduces the oxygen removal flux from the active sites. Consequently, water starvation may occur that could lead to both an increase of the membrane ionic resistance and the kinetic overpotential of the electrode.

Another cell element closely connected to the electrodes and influencing the performance is the microporous layer. Avoiding machined flow fields the MPL has to make sure that an optimum

transport of liquid to the reaction layer and removal of gases from the reaction layer is guaranteed even at high production rates. Furthermore, an optimized electrical connection to the electrode and membrane and to the bipolar layer is of importance. For the CCS (catalyst coated substrate) approach of making electrodes the PTL is even more intimately connected with the electrode. For optimized transport and electrical connection properties this project investigated to apply a microporous layer (MPL) on a variety of macroporous PTLs. This approach has shown interesting results as reported in the work from Razmoojei [8].

In this deliverable, different techniques to prepare the MEA will be presented with the various issues that we faced. A fully detailed description of the ink recipe and parameters will be disclosed.

2 First Approach: Catalyst coated Membranes

2.1 Ink formulations and MEA preparation

The ink formulation at CEA and DLR Oldenburg was deliberately close in order to cross-check the manufacturing reproducibility.

2.1.1 MEAs from DLR (Oldenburg)

Solutions of dissolved PSEBS in Toluene were sent to DLR(Oldenburg) and CEA by IMC. With FAA-3-SOLUT-10 from Fumatech, the PSEBS solutions were the two used ionomers to prepare the electrodes.

The first MEAs were based on Fumatech components (membrane and ionomer). The following Table 1 gives details and overview of the ink recipe.

Table 1. CCM electrodes recipes (Catalyst spray coating on the membrane)

	DLR 1. Batch		DLR 2. Batch	
	ANODE	CATHODE	ANODE	CATHODE
Catalyst	2,88 % Iridium	1,96 % Platinum	2.32% Iridium	1.75 % Platinum
Ionomer solution 5 wt. % FAA-3 in Ethanol	9.05%	6.18%	21.87%	16.50%
Solvent	88.06 %*	91.86%*	75.81 %*	81.75 %*

*solvent composition (water/ethanol (2/1 vol/vol))

From this batch three CCM were used and are shown on Figure 1. The first CCM-a was used as it is. The second CCM-b was hot pressed for 2 min at 120°C at 0.078 MPa and the last CCM-c was obtained by coating the membrane in the OH⁻ form (not in the Chloride form). This approach should avoid the chemical pre treatment in KOH 1M that could lead to electrode detachment from the membrane.

Figure 1. Picture of the three CCMs

Cell testing have shown low results in pure water (about 60 mA/cm² @ 2V) and was not tested in diluted KOH. In addition, severe delamination was observed after the pre activation in KOH solution.

Figure 2. CCM delamination after activation, MEAs from CEA

2.1.2 MEAs from CEA

The ink for the Doctor Blade coating has to be more viscous than the ink for spraying. Consequently, a viscous agent methyl cellulose was added. In the following tables Table 2 and Table 3 one may see the ink composition and the operating protocol to prepare the MEAs that are depicted on Figure 3.

Table 2. Ink recipes for CCM MEA by spray coating at CEA

	CEA	
	ANODE	CATHODE
Catalyst	3.6 % Iridium	1,4 % Pt/C (47 wt.% Platinum)
Ionomer solution 5 wt. % FAA-3 in Ethanol	16.00%	3.00%
Solvent	80.40%*	95.60%**

* anode solvent composition (water / ethanol (1 / 1) (vol/vol))

** cathode solvent composition (water / ethanol (2,5 / 1) (vol/vol))

Table 3. Detailed CCMs preparation at CEA

MEA	Coating Method	Quantity	Comments
FF07_DT#2	DT	x 1	80 wt.% catalyst - 20 wt.% ionomer (Fumion) DT parameters : 90 °C - 1.4 MPa - 10 min
FF06_DT#7	DT	x 1	80 wt.% catalyst - 15 wt.% ionomer (Fumion) - 5 % methycellulose DT parameters : 90 °C - 1.7 MPa - 3 min
FF06_DT#1	DT	x 1	80 wt.% catalyst - 10 wt.% ionomer (Fumion) - 5 % methycellulose DT parameters : 90 °C - 1.7 MPa - 3 min
FF03_BC	Bar Coating	x 3	80 wt.% catalyst - 10 wt.% ionomer (Fumion) - 10 % methycellulose
FF04_BC	Bar Coating	x 2	80 wt.% catalyst - 19 wt.% ionomer (Fumion) - 1 % methycellulose
FF05_BC	Bar Coating	x 2	80 wt.% catalyst - 15 wt.% ionomer (Fumion) - 5 % methycellulose

DT : Decal Transfer / BC: Bar coating

Figure 3. CCMs MEA

a) Doctor Blade coating CCM, b) Decal transfer CCM

2.2 MPL/PTL for CCM approach

By introducing a porous transport layer (PTL) into the cell with varying and well adapted porosity, transport processes can be improved and contact resistances reduced to achieve a lower cell overpotential. On the contact side to the electrode a layer with small pore sizes is needed, a microporous layer (MPL). At the same time material costs for the PTL need to be reduced. To achieve this, PTL made of stainless steel (SS) with a plasma-sprayed nickel MPL on top are produced and tested reducing the amount of more costly Nickel to a minimum.

In the first part of the project a variety of stainless steel grid substrates were coated with MPL and tested with the CCM membrane electrode assemblies. Two different single grids and one grid consisting of multiple, stacked grids of varying pore size were used. Figure 4 shows the MPL coated grid PTLs. The plasma spray process and parameters are described in Deliverable report D3.2. As shown in the tests of Figure 5 the MPL coated multilayer grid showed the best performance in pure water. This was continued to be used with further CCS in water and 0.1M KOH solution in a 4 cm² cell at DLR.

Figure 4. Picture of various vacuum plasma spray (VPS) MPL on different meshes

2.3 MEA testing

The MEA prepared by CEA and DLR(Oldenburg) were tested at DLR(Stuttgart) with the objective to observe the influence of the MEA as well as of various shapes of MPL coated meshes to the electrochemical response of the cell.

Three different MPLs were investigated.

Polarization curves comparison with Fumatech baseline components are shown on Figure 5.

Figure 5. Polarization curves CEA MEAs with various MPL structures in pure water at 45°C

The first observation is that the performance in pure water is very low with 60 mA/cm² at 2V for the highest results. In addition, we can also see that the mesh structure significantly influences the cell performance. From this result the multi-meshes seem to be the most promising component.

The MEAs from DLR were also tested and it was found that comparable low results were also obtained, as illustrated on [Figure 6](#).

Figure 6. Polarization curves comparison in pure water at 45°C

a) CCMs MEA from DLR, b) Comparison CEA and DLR(Oldenburg) MEA

Again, the results were far from our expectations and because the optimization of the Fumatech based MEA was out of scope of the project, it was decided to switch with materials of the NEWELY project.

Therefore a second set of MEAs was sent to DLR(Stuttgart)

The MEAs prepared by CEA in this second batch of shipping are gathered in Table 4.

Table 4. Summary of the second batch of MEA sent to DLR(Stuttgart)

Sample Name	Coating Method	Catalyst Anode / Ionomer	Catalyst Cathode / Ionomer	Comments
FF08_DT	Decal Transfer	OXYGN-N / PSEBS solution (5.9 mg/cm ²) / 5 wt.% in Toluene	H2GEN-M / PSEBS solution (7.6 mg/cm ²) / 5 wt.% in Toluene	Anode : 90 wt.% OXYGN-N 10 wt.% PSEBS Cathode : 95 wt.% H2GEN-M 5 wt.% PSEBS 5 wt.% Graphene
FF09_SPDT (Nafion in Cathode)	Spray on the cathode Decal Trasfert on the anode	OXYGN-N / PSEBS solution (5.15 mg/cm ²) / 5 wt.% in Toluene	H2GEN-M / Nafion D520 solution (8.4 mg/cm ²) / 5 wt.% in Ethanol water mixture	Anode : 90 wt.% OXYGN-N 10 wt.% PSEBS Cathode : 95 wt.% H2GEN-M 5 wt.% Nafion 5 wt.% Graphene
FF10_SPDT (Nafion+Graphene in cathode) (CeO ₂ in anode)	Spray on the cathode Decal Trasfert on the anode	OXYGN-N / PSEBS solution (5.9 mg/cm ²) / 5 wt.% in Toluene	H2GEN-M / Nafion D520 Solution (4.9 mg/cm ²) / 5 wt.% in Ethanol water mixture	Anode : 65.8 wt.% OXYGN-N 7.9 wt.% PSEBS 26.3 wt.% CeO ₂ Cathode : 89.6 wt.% H2GEN-M 5.5 wt.% Nafion 4.9 wt.% Graphene 5 wt.% Graphene

One may see that beside the change of raw materials (PSEBS membrane and CENmat catalysts) some modifications were made. On FF10_SPDT, cerine particles were added. It was reported [9] that CeO₂ has oxygen vacancies that may trap OH⁻ and improve oxygen evolution reaction (OER). Concerning the use of Nafion as cathode ionomer, Faïd and co-authors papers have reported the

benefit of using Nafion as ionomer because [10] ammonium group may adsorb on active sites and therefore hinder the HER to occur.

In the same way as CEA, DLR(Oldenburg) prepared CCM MEAs using direct spray coating onto the PSEBS membrane.

Table 5. Properties of CCM MEA from DLR(Oldenburg)

	Anode	Membrane	Cathode
Catalyst	OXYGN-N / PSEBS (93 / 7 wt.%) : 522 mg	60 μ m PSEBS	H2GEN-M / PSEBS (93 / 7 wt.%) : 522 mg
Ionomer	2 mg/cm ² OXYGN-N		2 mg/cm ² H2GEN-M

It was observed that the MEAs (FF09 and FF10) with Nafion ionomer have shown severe delamination, while MEA with PSEBS ionomer based MEA (FF08) did not show any evidence of active layer detachment as shown on Figure 7. The same trend was also confirmed with the MEA from DLR(Oldenburg) on which no delamination was observed.

Figure 7. Picture of CEA MEAs after chemical activation

a) No delamination CCM, b) Detached active layer MEA

The results in pure water were again quite low with 4V @80 mA/cm². The MEAs prepared at DLR(Oldenburg) were slightly better with 4V @ 400 mA/cm² and 2.25 V @ 400 mA/cm² in pure water and 0.1M KOH respectively.

Figure 8. Polarization curve of DLR MEA

a) In pure water, b) in 0.1M KOH

As decided based on these results, after the mid-term of the project, the base line electrolyte feedstock was 0.1M KOH at 50°C.

3 Second approach: Catalyst coated Substrates

3.1 MPL/PTL for CCS approach

For preparing electrodes via the CCS (catalyst coated substrate) approach a smooth substrate surface with small pores is needed. Following the project idea this should be a combined PTL with MPL, the PTL being stainless steel material, the MPL for durability reasons coated with Nickel. At the same time the substrate needed to have the right thickness to fit into the PTL space which is given in the Propuls cell and could not be changed for the single cell testing. To fulfil these requirements DLR selected stainless steel felts of 2 mm thickness that are quite compressible. They were coated with a Nickel MPL by Vacuum Plasma Spraying in the way described before. An alternative set of PTL/MPL was coated with Raney-Nickel i.e. NiAl-alloy, then leaching the aluminium to get a high nickel surface. Figure 9 shows a side view of the coated stainless steel felt. Then the MPL/PTL were sent to DLR (Oldenburg), compressed to their thickness as needed in the cell (1.3-1.4 mm) and electrodes were coated with ultrasonic spraying by the recipe that will be detailed below in the chapter on the CCS electrodes. (Refer to table 7).

Figure 9. Side view of stainless steel felt PTL with Nickel MPL coating on top side

These electrodes were sent to FBK for single cell tests in the Propuls cell. The single cell tests were conducted in comparison to tests of CCS electrodes coated on thin stainless steel felt with sintered titanium PTL.

However, there was a systematic error in all these tests, probably a reverse of the anode and cathode connection, leading to very poor performance in all these tests. It can only be concluded from these tests that all alternatives of PTL and electrodes behaved approximately in the same way. However, the purpose of optimizing the PTL and MPL is primarily relevant at high current densities. As these could not be reached in the tests it cannot be concluded if the MPL-coated stainless steel felt PTL give an improvement to other MPL and electrode substrates used in the project. As the testing and plasma spraying capacities in the project did not allow further tries with MPL/PTL, this research path was abandoned and is to be verified in later projects.

For the final single cell testing as well as the stack assembly the following electrode substrates and PTL are selected:

Anode electrode support: SS Bekipor 40BL3 ²(Bekaert)

Anode PTL: SS PTL by Haver³ for anode

² Felt, material stainless steel 316L, 230 µm thickness, 12 µm fibres, 84 % Porosity

³ Haver&Boecker Haver POROSTAR, 5-La 5µm, material Stainless steel 1.4404, filter material, sintered woven SS fibre grids, 5 layers of various pore thickness, minimum pore size 5 µm, thickness approx. 1.7

Cathode electrode support: Avcarb⁴ MGL370 Carbon paper

Cathode PTL: LinqCell graphite for cathode⁵

3.2 CCS electrodes preparation and single cell testing (4-25 cm²)

3.2.1 At CEA

For sake of simplicity, it was also decided to mainly focus on MEA production with CCS-type MEA. As reported in the report D3.4, the content of PSEBS also greatly impacts the electrochemical performances. Based on these analyses, at CEA it was decided to fix the catalyst/ionomer ratio to 97/3 wt%.

An example of the ink formulation is gathered in Table 6

Table 6. CCS electrode CEA recipes

	Anode recipe	Cathode Recipe
Catalyst	OXYGN-N : 522 mg	H2GEN-M : 550 mg
Ionomer	PSEBS solution@ 5wt.% in Toluene : 323 mg	PSEBS solution@ 5wt.% in Toluene : 339 mg
Solvent	Toluene : 9 000mg	Toluene : 9 000mg
Solid content	5.40%	5.40%

The ink was spray coated on 5,3x 5.3 cm² Bekaert felt (40 BL3) on the anode and on Avcarb GDL on the cathode. The final loading was 3.4 mg/cm² (95 mg of OXYGEN-N).

With these electrodes the NEWELY milestone was outperformed as it can be seen on Figure 10.

Figure 10. Polarization curve in 25cm² Propuls cell

⁴ <https://www.avcarb.com/product-page-mgl/> AvCarb® Molded Graphite Laminates (MGL) are superior carbon papers designed for electrolyzer and fuel cell applications. Porosity 78 %, thickness 0.370 mm

⁵ Thickness 1.5 mm, density 0.6 kg/m³, <https://www.caplinc.com/gdl1500-1.5mm-graphitized-carbon-plate-for-gas-diffusion-layers-gdl1500.html?filter=76523>

Additional improvement was suggested with the increase of the catalyst loading. Using the exactly same recipe but by increasing the catalyst loading from roughly 3 mg/cm² to above 5 mg/cm² we have reached 2 A/cm² @ 2V (but with Sustainion X37-RT) membrane as shown on **Figure 11**.

Figure 11. Highest performances with highly loaded electrodes in 2cm² single cell

3.2.2 At DLR

At DLR various anodes and cathodes with an active area of 25 cm² were produced on the substrates Bekipor 40BL3 and Avcarb MGL317 with the improved catalyst inks (in Table 8). Both anode and cathode had a catalyst loading of 5 mg cm⁻² and an catalyst:ionomer ratio of 93:7.

The coating parameters that were used for depositing the catalyst layers are shown in Table 7. The substrates were placed on a heat plate with a temperature of 60°C to dry the catalyst layer during the coating procedure. To reach the desired catalyst loading, various layers (130-160) were deposited. The spray pattern is shown in Figure 12. For a more homogeneous catalyst layer, the spray pattern is run successively in 4 different directions.

Table 7 Coating parameters for the production of the 200 cm² NEWELY CCS

Flow rate	Nozzle Frequency	Distance to the substrate	Nozzle speed	Line Spacing	Temperature of Heat Plate
0.5 ml/min	48 Khz	45 mm	70 mm/s	4 mm	60 °C

Figure 12 Spray pattern for depositing the catalyst layers of NEWELY anode and cathode

Figure 13 Electrodes with an active area of 25 cm²: a) Cathodes (H2GEN-M™ catalyst and PSEBS ionomer on AvCarb MGL 370 carbon paper), b) Anodes (OXYGN-N™ catalyst and PSEBS ionomer on Bekipor 40BL3 stainless steel felt)

Table 8. DLR ink recipe

Anode	Cathode
1 167 mg OXYGN-N	1 333 mg H2GEN-M
1 750 mg PSEBS solution (5 wt.% in CHCl ₃)	2 000 mg PSEBS solution (5 wt.% in CHCl ₃)
140 ml CHCl ₃	160 ml CHCl ₃
5 mg/cm ²	5 mg/cm ²
57 %	62 %

Solid content: 1.3%

In order to coat a substrate the amount of catalyst needed in the ink is about three times higher than the deposited amount, which means that the loss of catalysts is around 60%. That leads to less waste materials than the ink from CEA. In addition, it could be also seen that the solid content is much lower at DLR in comparison with the CEA recipe.

Unfortunately, it is impossible to ship chloroform based solution. Consequently, only DLR(Oldenburg) is able to prepare electrodes based on dissolved PSEBS in Chloroform.

The inks prepared with Toluene did not show severe settling at CEA, but it seems that Chloroform is a better solvent.

25 cm² CCS electrodes were sent to CEA and FBK for ageing test and after the qualification of those electrodes, 200 cm² electrodes were manufactured for the stack assembly.

3.3 CCS stack electrodes preparation (200 cm²)

200 cm² Electrodes were prepared using the same deposition and ink parameters compared to the 25 cm² electrodes.

In Figure 14 the final anodes and cathodes are shown. In total, six anodes and six cathodes were produced and sent to WHS for the assembly of the final 5-cell AEMWE stack.

Figure 14 Electrodes with an active area of 200 cm²; left: Anode (OXYGN-N™ catalyst and PSEBS ionomer on Bekipor 40BL3 stainless steel felt), right: Cathode (H2GEN-M™ catalyst and PSEBS ionomer on AvCarb MGL 370 carbon paper)

4 Conclusion

As a conclusion, several strategies were pursued to prepare electrodes, either for CCS MEAs or CCM MEAs. Despite performances below our expectations in pure water, it contributes to disseminate various ways to prepare electrodes. The main conclusion and issues are reported below.

- 1) For the manufacturing with spray coating technique, the PSEBS ionomer should be preferentially dissolved in chloroform
- 2) Alternatively Toluene may be considered as a suitable solvent but less effective than chloroform
- 3) CCM MEA based on spray coating onto Fumatech membranes lead to severe delamination during pre activation in KOH solution
- 4) CCM prepared by decal transfer (with a hot pressing step) did not show delamination
- 5) Bar coating deposition requires a more viscous ink solution. Therefore, a viscous agent was added, methyl cellulose. With a weight ratio 80/1 catalyst/methyl cellulose, it was possible to coat the ink directly onto the Fumatech membrane or to proceed to the decal transfer method.
- 6) Light decal transfer method was found that consist in applying 90°C – 1,7 MPa for 3 min to complete the transfer. This protocol is more soft conditions when compared with transfer condition with PFSA membranes which are hot pressed at 120 ~ 135 °C. Despite the successful MEA preparation, the performances were quite low in pure water but not tested in diluted KOH solution at early age of the project.
- 7) CCS electrodes with CENmat catalysts OXYGN-N and H2GEN-M on anode and cathode respectively were successfully mixed with PSEBS ionomer to prepare MEAs that were tested and have shown a current density above 1A/cm² @ 2V in 0.1 M KOH at 50°C. The MEAs do not contain PGM materials.
- 8) CCS electrodes were successfully upscaled to 200cm² active area and six anodes and six cathodes were prepared for the AEMWE stack.

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